

Notas breves

Collatus (Gastropoda: Vitrinellidae): formal description and designation of its type species

Collatus (Gastropoda: Vitrinellidae): descripción formal y designación de su especie tipo

Federico RUBIO* & Emilio ROLÁN**

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The genus *Collatus* was published as a new genus in RUBIO & ROLÁN (2018a). Nevertheless, the designation of its type species was accidentally omitted, therefore not fulfilling one of the requirements of ICZN for availability:

“13.3. Genus-group names. To be available, every new genus-group name published after 1930 (...) must, in addition to satisfying the provisions of Article 13.1, be accompanied by the fixation of a type species in the original publication”.

A correction was published (RUBIO & ROLÁN 2018b) but there another requirement of ICZN was not fulfilled and the name remained unavailable:

“16.1. All names: intention of authors to establish new nominal taxa to be explicit. Every new name published after 1999, including new replacement names (nomina nova), must be explicitly indicated as intentionally new [by an expression such as “new genus” or “n. gen.]”

Therefore, the full descriptions with the required indications is here reissued.

Collatus new genus

Type species: *Collatus regularis* Rubio & Rolán, 2018: 16 (fig. 1A-G).

Description: Shell turbiniform, with a depressed or to little high spire; protoconch multispiral ornamented with thick flexuous oblique riblets; teleoconch totally covered by spiral cords, adapically thicker and separated from each other, and abapically much thinner and numerous. Growth lines strongly prosocline. Spaces between cords totally

covered by micro granules. Aperture rounded; margin of the outer lip modified by spiral cords. Umbilicus widely opened, totally covered by fine spiral cords inside.

Remarks: The shells included in this genus are rather similar, all sharing the main characters that are the protoconch with about 2 whorls, ornamented with

* Pintor Ribera, 4-16^a, 46930 Quart de Poblet (Valencia), Spain. federubio@ono.com

** Museo de Historia Natural, Parque Vista Alegre, Campus Universitario Norte, 15782 Santiago de Compostela, Spain. emiliorolan@gmail.com

thick flexuous oblique riblets and the teleoconch totally covered by two types of spiral cords regularly distributed and a thickening outer lip.

Circulus Jeffreys, 1865 is the genus whose species *Circulus chosiensis* has a similar shape to that of the *Collatus* species. However, the genus *Circulus* is very different, its differential morphological characters being: protoconch without axial folds, teleoconch with uniformly thick spiral cords, both adapical and abapically, and a wide and deep umbilicus.

Monodosus Rubio & Rolán, 2016 is the only genus whose species have a

similar protoconch, but the rest of the morphological characters are totally different (shell discoidal, much flattened and strongly keeled, with adapical nodes on the teleoconch whorls).

The above mentioned circumstances do not affect the availability of the six specific names published by Rubio & Rolán (2018a), following provisions of ICZN:

11.9.3. A species-group name must be published in unambiguous combination with a generic name (...)

11.9.3.1. the generic name need not be valid or even available.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

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RUBIO F. & ROLÁN E. 2018a. *Collatus* a new genus of the Family Vitrinellidae (Gastropoda: Truncatellidae) from the Pacific Ocean, with the description of 6 new species. *Gloria Maris*, 57 (1): 15-28.

RUBIO F. & ROLÁN E. 2018b. A type species for the genus *Collatus* Rubio & Rolán, 2018 (Gastropoda: Vitrinellidae). *Gloria Maris*, 57 (2): 64.